

PERIODONTAL DISEASE AND THEIR INCIDENCE LEVELS IN PAINT SHOP WORKERS

Nortaev Azamat Begmatovich, Usmanov Ravshan Djakhongirovich

Assistant, Professor, Tashkent medical academy, Tashkent

E-mail: azamatnortoyev27@gmail.com, usmanovravshan65@gmail.com

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Abstract. *The article describes periodontal diseases, their frequency and negative consequences in workers working in paint shops. Nowadays, we can see the expansion of the volume of work in paint shops of light industry in almost all regions of our Republic. Chemical dyes and reagents have been found to contain more than 70 organic and inorganic elements. These chemical compounds cause various damage to the body of workers, especially the tissues of the oral cavity and teeth. As a result, the clinical course of the pathological process in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity and the hard tissue of the tooth leads to the study of its normal state.*

Key words: *periodontism, paint, sex, male, female, mucosa, control, group.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada bo‘yoq sexlarida ishlovchi ishchilarda paradont kasalliklari, ularning uchrash darajalari va salbiy oqibatlari haqida berilgan. Hozirgi kunda Respublikamizning deyarli barcha hududlarida yengil sanoatning bo‘yoq sexlarida ish hajmining kengayib borishini ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Kimyoviy bo‘yoqlar va reagentlar tarkibida 70 dan ortiq organik va anorganik elementlar borligi aniqlangan. Bu kimyoviy birikmalar ish xodimlarni organizmiga, ayniqsa og‘iz bo‘shlig‘i to‘qimalariga hamda tishlarga turli xil zarar yetkazadi. Oqibatda og‘iz bo‘shlig‘i shilliq qavati va tish qattiq to‘qimasida patologik jarayonning klinik kechishi hamda normal holatini o‘rgarishiga olib keladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *paradont, bo‘yoq, sex, erkak, ayol, shilliq qavat, nazorat, guruh.*

Today, manufacturing enterprises occupy leading positions in many developed countries of the world (1,2). Not only diseases of the respiratory system, but also diseases of the oral cavity took the leading place among the workers working in these enterprises (2,3). For example, periodontal disease is common. Factors such as vibration, noise, air dust and chemical contamination, changes in air temperature in the working conditions of employees working with chemical paints have a direct and indirect effect on the body of workers, causing a decrease in general and local immunity, as a result, the human body and oral cavity are affected. It causes changes in the functional states of bones and tissues (2,3).

The purpose of the study. Study of periodontal diseases and their occurrence levels in workers working in paint shops.

Research materials and methods. We selected 55 employees working in paint shops and 15 employees who were not in contact with various paints (control group) as research objects. We divided the employees of the paint shops into 2 groups: female and male employees. We studied the employees of the working group based on the information of the medical card "Employees' primary dental examination card" maintained by the company's nurse.

The results of the study. As a result of the studies, it was clear that the percentage of periodontal diseases in the employees of paint shops was higher in female employees than in male employees. Along with periodontal disease, workers of paint shops also suffered from leukoplakia, stomatitis, and various inflammations in the oral cavity. For example, periodontal

diseases were found in 11 (20%) employees with up to 4 years of work experience in paint shops, among them (5 male employees, 6 female employees).

Table 1

Also, periodontal diseases were found in 14 (25%) employees with 7 years of work experience in paint shops, among them (6 men and 8 women). In the control group, it was observed in 5 employees (33%). As a result of the employees, "Employees' primary health card" and observations, it became clear that 30 (54.5%) of the employees with 9 years of work experience had periodontal diseases, of which (11 men and 15 women) were employees. It was observed in 7 employees (46.7%) in the control group. In addition, a decrease in the level of electrical excitability in the dental hard tissue was observed among employees working with chemical paints. We can see a decrease in electrical excitation in the central teeth. Similar results were reported for molars and molars.

When the control groups were examined, regardless of the anatomical shape of the teeth, the same results were noted in the spade tooth and in the molar and food teeth.

Table 2

As can be seen from the diagrams, we can see that inflammations in the oral cavity and teeth are stronger in women than in men. The years also took their toll on chemical paint workers. The increase in the volume of work caused the increase in periodontal diseases.

Conclusion. 1. As a result of observations, it became clear that periodontal diseases are more common in women than in men.
 2. Not only periodontal disease, but also inflammation of the oral cavity, leukoplakia, and stomatitis were found in certain percentages among the employees of paint shops.
 3. Not only diseases of the oral cavity, but also inflammation of the respiratory organs, especially the lungs, are observed in workers of paint shops.

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